

ORGANIZATION OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN TWO DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RUSSIAN FEDERATION AND JAPAN

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Abstract: Education has become one of the indispensable and most important parts of our life, therefore, every country should pay great attention to education from infancy to adulthood. It serves to make the citizens of the country mature and capable in all aspects. The stage of preschool education, which is considered the initial level of education, is organized in different ways in each country. In this article, we will study the system of preschool education in the Russian Federation and Japan. Specific aspects of the educational system of two different countries are mentioned.

Keywords: Russian Federation, Japan, Early childhood education and care, Educational Public Policy, Ministry of Education, Stages of general Education.

Education is an important thing and very influential in life. According to Freeman Butt, in the Cultural History of Western Education, education is also a growth process to develop the talents, strengths, abilities, and interests of an individual so that various kinds of abilities and capabilities are formed (Wijana, 2008: 126).

Education is a process to change the identity of a student to be more advanced. According to experts, there are several definitions that explore the definition of education itself. For example, education means maintaining and giving training. In maintaining practice, it is necessary to have teachings, guidance, and leadership regarding morals and intelligence of the mind (Mustofa, 2015: 6).

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guidance, and leadership regarding morals and intelligence of the mind (Mustofa, 2015: 6).

Introduction: The opportunities and challenges we face in the classroom have a profound effect on our development as people. According to Freeman Butt, author of "Cultural History of Western Education," education is more than just a means of acquiring knowledge; it's also a means of cultivating an individual's unique set of skills, interests, and aptitudes.

Education is the means through which a person grows into a more complete version of themselves. Experts say there are a lot of ways to define education that each probe different aspects of the idea of schooling. Maintenance and dissemination of training are intertwined in a number of fields; education is only one example. Ethical and intellectual concerns need guidance, direction, and leadership if we are to maintain a consistent practise.

Learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, and learning to live together are the four cornerstones of a well-rounded education according to UNESCO. Putting it another way, people need to keep learning even after they finish school. One way to improve the quality of the workforce is via educational opportunities. The purpose of education is to help students realise their full potential by fostering the conditions necessary for learning and the growth of their self-discipline, personality, intelligence, noble character, and talents that may be used throughout their lives. Education is the means through which this objective is achieved. To create a generation of high-quality, inventive, and morally upstanding individuals, education must begin at a young age, in this case starting with early childhood education.

In this article, we will highlight the attention paid to the preschool education system, its development and the main components of the educational system in the Russian Federation and Japan.

Main part: In the Russian Federation, preschool is included in the standard curriculum for all children. The Russian government is committed to ensuring that all children in the country have access to quality of early education. The government offers a free, optional preschool programme to families. There are two options of pre-school education (table-1):

Home-based pre-school education	Center-based pre-school education
Some families choose to educate their children at home, either via a preschool programme that offers	Although children as young as two months may enroll in center-based preschool programmes, public

home visits or through a private home schooling organisation.	preschool education services typically do not include infant and toddler programmes.
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Table-1: Forms of pre-school education in Russian Federation

The quality of the process is strongly correlated with the parameters that positively effects the quality of the structure: the quality of the technique is significantly correlated with the instructor's credentials, namely a bachelor's degree in early childhood education; teachers' access to professional development opportunities, such as a wide variety of in-service training programmes, is crucial. with respect to employee in-service education, a very substantial positive correlation was found; the importance of a kindergarten's organisational culture, management, and team-building initiatives cannot be overstated.[2]

Expanding access to and coverage of full-time, center-based preschool for children ages three to seven is the primary emphasis of the government's initiatives to increase preschool education accessibility and coverage, which account for the whole of these efforts. Primary school may be started anywhere between the ages of six and a half and eight years old for a kid. Children as young as two months old and as old as seven years old can now be cared for in a group setting and supervised in a preschool environment, thanks to a recent change in federal education legislation. This makes it possible to provide preschool-like environments for children without actually having to implement a preschool curriculum. Legally, preschool-aged children may get their education in governmental as well as private schools.

Due to the multilevel governance structure that exists in the Russian Federation, the responsibility for Early Childhood Education at the national level is shared between the Ministries of Education, Health, and Work and Employment, in addition to various cross-cutting departmental bodies. Children have the legal right to receive care and education that is publicly financed and provided by the public sector. Paid and unpaid parental leave options, including maternity and paternity leave, are legal entitlements in several countries. Many aspects of early childhood programmes are regulated at the local level, while others are the responsibility of the state or federal government. Because the workforce draws from the health, care, and education sectors, and these professionals are frequently well skilled in their own professions, issues of staff credentials, training, and remuneration may get tangled. Methodists, speech therapists,

psychologists, music educators, PE instructors, general educators, general educator aides, junior educators, and junior educator aides are all examples of these types of workers. Furthermore, three distinct styles of leadership exist.

Children acquire social-cultural experience in part by mastering what Vygotskians called “cultural tools” – oral and written language, number systems, etc. Because these tools initially exist as external forms like objects and representations it is especially important for educators to provide young children with carefully designed and stimulating environments.[1]

Preschool and kindergarten programmes in the Russian Federation are guided by a national curriculum framework. This policy promotes a well-rounded education that caters to students' cognitive, affective, behavioural, and social needs as well as their physical, cognitive, affective, behavioural, and social needs through instruction in areas such as language, communication, reading, writing, mathematics, the natural world, science, technology, and the digital world. There is also mandatory advice on pedagogical practises that is uniform across all preschool age groups and is issued either at the national or subnational level. To name just a few examples, we have the creative/progressive curriculum, the experiential curriculum, the play curriculum, and the child-centered approach grounded on Vygotsky's cultural-historical theory. The curriculum also includes time for play.

Both information-transmission guidelines and parental participation in their children's schooling contribute to the success of the latter. Despite the lack of accreditation processes, all early childhood education facilities are subject to inspection by regional or local agencies. The inspection is primarily concerned with the deal's quality, the financial situation's feasibility, and the adherence to rules. Both the organisations in responsibility of the settings and the regional entities in charge of the settings are informed of the results of the quality assurance procedure. The results are also made available online.

Even though preschool attendance is not mandated in Japan, the country has a far higher enrolment rate (over 90%) than the Russian Federation. Starting at age 3, these institutions aim to strengthen students' cognitive capacities in preparation for the subsequent six years of primary school. A child's preschool education may be delivered by either a kindergarten, which is considered to be a school, or a day care centre, which is considered to be a sort of welfare institution under the Child Welfare Law's definition. The statute makes reference to both public and private entities.

Not only can early childhood education and care programmes vary greatly in structure from country to country, but also in terms of the ages of children who

attend different types of settings or the extent to which children engage in different settings. The Japanese government funds both academic-only and holistic early childhood education and care initiatives. ECED programmes are not available in Japan, however children aged 3-5 do participate in pre-primary education. These initiatives also include programmes at day care centres other than kindergartens.

Broad legislative protections for participation in early childhood education and care, as well as programmes to provide free access for particular age and demographic groups, provide strong backing for the field. This makes it possible for people to take part in programmes providing care for and educating young children. Low-income families in Japan are eligible for free kindergarten enrollment for 55 hours per week and free childcare enrollment for 20 hours per week.

There are four distinguishing features of Japanese preschools that may be identified.

1. Together, academics from universities and other such organisations and those who deal directly with young children in the classroom analyse and improve early childhood education. Many educators who begin their careers in the classroom move on to pursue careers as researchers or vocational instructors at universities, junior colleges, or vocational institutes as a consequence of their further education or professional success. There are a few possible explanations for this2.

2. There are many different philosophical schools in the area of early childhood education, all of which use different pedagogical strategies. In real practise, however, these strands are not imposed inflexibly but rather with flexibility, according to an approach that is carefully adjusted to the lives and behaviours of each kid. The age, gender, race, and socioeconomic condition of the kid are only a few of the variables considered.3.

3. ECE pedagogies may be found over a broad spectrum. Different kindergartens develop their own approaches to early childhood education by combining and adapting elements from a variety of models, or by starting from scratch and starting small. Methods of this kind might be developed via the fruitful interplay of varied material and approach. However, there are some kindergartens that refuse to try new approaches and instead stubbornly adhere to the ways they've always done things.

4. There is a strong collaborative relationship between the classroom and the institution where future educators are trained in the subject of early childhood education. Educator preparation programmes at universities, community

colleges, and professional schools not only prepare teachers for the classroom but also aim to support it by developing effective teaching methods.

In Japan, infants and toddlers are primarily cared for and educated through kindergartens and daycare centres (table-2).

Kindergartens	Daycare centers
Kindergartens provide three years of care and education for children three years of age or older, who go on to enter elementary school after finishing kindergartens.	Daycare centers accept children under elementary school age.

Table-2: Difference between kindergartens and daycare centers.

Early childhood in Japan must be educated with an education system that can bring out superior characters such as discipline, responsibility, mutual cooperation, and not easily give up. Early childhood in Japan must be educated with an education system that can bring out superior characters such as discipline, responsibility, mutual cooperation, and not easily give up.

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Most children of elementary school age attend either kindergarten or a daycare centre. General frameworks for early childhood education are provided by the Ministries of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology and Health and Labor and Welfare; however, the specifics of early childhood education are left up to each individual kindergarten or daycare centre, leading to a wide range of approaches (Figure-1).

Figure-1: Approaches of Early childhood care

Kindergarten curricula are based on guidelines set out by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology and are referred to as the Course of Study for Kindergarten. Early childhood care and education at daycare centres, on the other hand, are governed by the Guidelines for Nursery Care at Day Nursery, which are mandated by the Ministry of Health, Labor, and Welfare. The content that should be included in early childhood care and education is comparable in each of these Guidelines. Furthermore, there are stringent regulations that must be met in regards to the construction and design of buildings and other infrastructure. However, unlicensed daycare centres may be opened if they meet regulations that are less stringent than those for licenced institutions. Both governmental and private organisations may house kindergartens and daycare centres. The costs of childcare at private facilities are covered by the parents' tuition payments and public funding. However, government dollars help subsidise public preschools and childcare centres. Public kindergartens are supervised by the local government's educational committee, and the Supervisor is in charge of providing guidance on how to put early childhood care and education into practise. Most efforts to improve early childhood education and care training are the responsibility of autonomous networks of private schools. The local government has a department dedicated to overseeing private kindergartens that are independently owned and run. Since private schools are not required to have as high a standard for teacher education, many of their kindergartens provide a wide choice of curricular options. It's worth noting that many administrative personnel and those in charge of teacher education have themselves served as kindergarten educators, and that many of them have returned to the classroom after serving in administrative roles.

Conclusion: To sum up, the system of pre-school education in both countries is very well organized. However, their principles, goals, programs, etc. differ from each other. If the involvement and active participation with children in the learning process of parents in the educational process in the Russian Federation attracted our attention, the demand and the enthusiasm of citizens for preschool education in Japan inspired us. The two countries we have studied can serve as an example for the education system of other countries.

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